

PIZZAIA, Cassiana; ZAHARA, Rima Awada; VILAS BOAS, Rosi. **O Haiti de Jean** [Jean's Haiti]. Illustrations: Angelo Abu. São Paulo: Brasil, 2019.

REVIEW¹

Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro²

Teen book Jean's Haiti is a tale of the misfortunes endured by Jean and his family while fleeing from Haiti in the wake of the 2010 earthquake that devastated the country, and of their efforts to get to Brazil in search of a better life. The story highlights the suffering of Haitian families who were forced to migrate following the disaster, many of them to Brazil. The book was written by a journalist, a psychologist, and a librarian and illustrated by Angelo Abu.

Keywords: Politics. Social questions. Human rights.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2020 Bologna. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

² Voter.